

Continuous Systematic Review in Software Engineering

The main objective of this research project is to propose and evaluate a process and guideline solution called **Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR)** to support the update of **Systematic Literature reviews (SLR)** in **Software Engineering (SE)**.

As part of this ongoing research project in Evidence-Based Software Engineering, we would appreciate a lot having your valuable feedback.

There are 34 questions in this survey.

Which of these profiles do you most identify with?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I am a researcher in the field of software engineering
- I am a professor (or senior researcher) in the field of software engineering
- I am a Ph.D. student in the field of software engineering
- I am a master's student in the field of software engineering
- I am an undergraduate student in the field of software engineering
- Other

How many SLRs have you published in a conference or journal?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4 or more

How many SLR Updates have you conducted?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4 or more

Among the SLR updates you conducted, how many of them were published?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4 or more

Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR) Process

[1] B. M. Napoleão, F. Petrillo, S. Hallé, M. Kalinowski, Towards continuous systematic literature review in software engineering, in: 48th EuroMicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), 2022.

Decision point 1: Does the SLR have a published update or replication?

The first step to conducting an SLR update is to identify whether or not there are updates or replications of this published SLR [1, 2]. Identifying whether there are any SLR updates or replications is crucial to avoid conducting an unnecessary update. In addition, the protocol information of all versions of the SLR should be considered due to they are crucial for decision-making in the update process; for example: (i) the period covered by the original SLR and its respective updates in order to be able to perform a search for new evidence accurately; (ii) if the SLR was replicated and the differences between the protocol information and the result of the original SLR and replication.

SLRs updates and replications were published after the original SLR, and usually, they cite the original SLR. In order to identify if there is a published SLR update or a replication of the SLR under investigation, we suggest locating the SLR under review on Google Scholar Digital Library and checking its citations aiming to find updates or replications.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding decision point 1 “Does the SLR have a published update or replication?”. How much do you agree with this point?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Full CSLR guidelines and process with references

(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvpK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR) Process

Activity 1: Obtain the SLR protocol information (all versions)

After identifying all published versions of an SLR, its updates, and replications (if they exist), the next activity is to extract the protocol information of all considered studies and organize and store them in a database. The protocols information includes the following:

Research Questions: All the research questions addressed by the original SLR, updates and replications (if exists).

Search Strategy: The search methods adopted by the original SLR, updates, and replications, for instance, automated search on digital libraries and/or manual search and/or snowballing. For automated searches, it must include the search string (also the adapted search strings for each digital library, if available) and the chosen digital libraries [9]. For manual searches, the list of venues where the manual search was performed (and the web page links of these venues, if available). Finally, for snowballing, the list of studies considered as “seed set”, the snowballing performed (backward or forward), and the number of iterations performed.

Search Period: The covered search period information is crucial to determine what years the search performed by the original SLR, SLR update, and replications cover and what period the new update must cover [9]. Also, in this step, we recommend elaborating a timeline with the years covered by the considered SLR studies. The timeline enables a time view of the years considered by the SLRs and the gap between updates or replications. We recommend that the search period for a (new) update covers at least one month retroactive of the informed search period. Nevertheless, several published SLRs and updates did not mention the search period. In these cases, we suggest that the search period to be considered is one year retroactive to the year of publication of the SLR. These temporal measures are suggested to mitigate the risk of losing relevant evidence. In order to facilitate future detection of the search period covered by the new SLR update in progress, we suggest adding the covered search period as an inclusion or exclusion criteria statement as performed in [17, 23, 24].

Selection Criteria: The selection criteria used by the original SLR should be used in updates [9]. The selection criteria comprise inclusion criteria, exclusion criteria, and quality criteria. In practice, most of the SLR updates published in SE used the same inclusion and exclusion criteria adopted in the original SLR.

In summary, we recommend applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria and quality criteria (if available) presented in the original SLR, replications, and updates on the new SLR update. Nonetheless, suppose there are divergences among the criteria presented in the SLR versions. In that case, they should be analyzed and discussed by the SLR authors of the new update in progress and through consensus to take decisions and document them explicitly in the new update.

List of Included Studies: The list of included primary studies by the original SLR, updates, and replications is a vital asset to be used as a “seed set” for performing the snowballing forward technique for a new update [8]. In addition, it could be used as an instrument of reanalysis for the authors conducting the new update to acquire knowledge on the investigated SLR topic [9].

Synthesis Method: According to Mendes et al. [1], an SLR update can include a more recent meta-analysis or research synthesis method or even follow the same synthesis method adopted by the original SLR. Analyzing some SLR updates published in SE, we noticed that most updates compare results between the original and the updated SLR. This approach aims to present changes and advances in relation to the research questions investigated. Among examples of SLR updates that performed comparisons between previous and updated versions are [5, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18, 20, 24, 25].

It is essential to mention that all this extracted protocol information should also be reported in the current update, as this information will be crucial for the success of future updates [9]. Unfortunately, transferring know-how from the SLR conduction is still tricky, even with the protocol data available. However, external repositories such as GitHub, Zenodo, or ArXiv are options to mitigate the lack of space and problems linked to SLR protocol information availability [32].

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Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding activity 1 “Obtain the SLR protocol information (all versions)?”. How much do you agree with this activity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Full CSLR guidelines and process with references

(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvepK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

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Activity 2: Execute one forward snowballing search iteration

Snowballing consists of looking for relevant studies by analyzing the list of references (snowballing backward) or citations (snowballing forward) of a pre-selected group of studies (“seed set”) that can be obtained by other search methods such as automated or manual search. The promising results of using snowballing forward to update SLRs in SE were recently investigated by Wohlin et al. [8]. This study demonstrated that only one iteration of the forward snowballing technique using as “seed set” the included studies of the original SLR with the Google Scholar search engine was the most cost-effective approach to search for new evidence for SLR updates. Therefore, we suggest conducting this approach to search for new evidence to update SLRs in SE.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding activity 2 “Execute one forward snowballing search	○	○	○	○	○

iteration". How much do you agree with this activity?

Full CSLR guidelines and process with references

(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvpK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR) Process

- Legend:**
- Activity (or portion) dependent on automation (not described in the guidelines)
 - Activity that can be performed manually (described in the guidelines)
 - Decision point
 - Start
 - End

Adapted from [1]

[1] B. M. Napoleão, F. Petriolo, S. Hajri, M. Kalinowski, Towards continuous systematic literature review in software engineering, in: 48th EuroMicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), 2022.

Decision point 2: Is any candidate study detected?

The purpose of this decision point is to verify if any study returned from the execution of the snowballing forward activity (candidate study). If yes, the following process activity is triggered.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding decision point 2 “Is any candidate study detected?”. How much do you agree with this point?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

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Activity 3: Apply the Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria (IC/EC) on title, abstract and keywords

Differently from this consecutive two-part traditional selection process proposed for SLRs by Kitchenham et al. [29], we propose for SLR updates performing only the first part: select candidates studies based only on title abstract and keywords. The second part of the process should be performed during the SLR update execution activity (Activity 6). We chose this approach because we aim to reduce efforts during the selection activity. At this stage of the CSLR process, we do not even know if the SLR needs to be updated. This need is evaluated when verifying if the SLR or the SLR update needs to be updated (Decision point 4).

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding activity 3 “Apply the Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria (IC/EC) on title, abstract and keywords”. How much do you agree with this activity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

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Decision point 3: Is there any potential relevant study?

This decision point aims to verify if, after applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Activity 3), potentially relevant studies should be further analyzed and trigger the next process activity (Activity 4 - Make the information available to potential stakeholders).

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding decision point 3 “Is there any potential relevant study?”. How much do you agree with this point?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR) Process

[1] B. M. Napoleão, F. Petrillo, S. Hallé, M. Kalinowski, Towards continuous systematic literature review in software engineering, in: 48th EuroMicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), 2022.

Activity 4: Make the information available to potential stakeholders

Over the last few years, the open science movement has gained importance in SE. It consists of making research artifacts available to the public addressing open access, open data, and open-source practices [32]. Open Science (OS) practices can directly impact SLR update conduction. The access and availability of primary evidence positively affect the maintainability of SLRs. Thus, researchers should address OS practices in any Evidence-Based Software Engineering (EBSE) study.

In this sense, in this activity, we recommend making all the information extracted from all SLR protocol versions (Activity 1) and the list of candidate studies (Activity 3) available online. While there is no dedicated repository to manage these data, we suggest adding them to open dissemination repositories such as Zenodo or Github, where this data can be freely accessed and updated, if necessary [32].

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding activity 4 “Make the information available to potential stakeholders”. How much do you agree with this activity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Full CSLR guidelines and process with references

(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvpK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

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Decision point 4: Does the SLR pass the criteria of the 3PDF Framework?

Before proceeding with an SLR update, deciding whether an SLR needs updating is essential. Mendes et al. [1] proposed and evaluated the adoption of a framework to support this decision in their study. The 3PDF Framework is a three-step method composed of seven questions to

be answered based on the SLR candidate to update.

In this activity, the researcher aims to perform an SLR update and must submit the SLR to all questions and decision sieves described in the 3PDF Framework. Examples of SLR updates that needed updates evaluated using the 3PDF Framework are described in [1].

Nevertheless, the results obtained by executing the 3PDF framework should be shared in an open repository, preferably in the same repository where all the other information about the SLR update under investigation is stored.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding decision point 4 “Does the SLR pass the criteria of the 3PDF Framework?”. How much do you agree with this point?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Full CSLR guidelines and process with references

(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvepK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

**Continuous Systematic Literature Review
(CSLR) Process**

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Activity 5: Contact the SLR authors

This activity reports the results obtained by conducting the previous activities to potential stakeholders, especially by verifying the need to update the SLR (Decision point 4). Studies [9, 34] highlight the importance of having the participation of at least one author of the previous version of the SLR in its update process. In practice, the following SLR updates included at least one author of the original SLR in the updated version: [5, 15–17, 23, 24, 31]. Moreover, a few SLR updates have the same authors as the original SLR: [10, 27, 28].

From this perspective, we suggest contacting potential stakeholders (i.e., authors of the SLRs' older versions) to disseminate the results of this analysis: If the need for updating the SLR is positive, instead verify a possible interest in contribution with the SLR update under evaluation by the current researcher or share the need for an SLR update with these authors, informing that the researcher will not perform the SLR update. If the need for updating the SLR is negative, no contact is necessary.

*

Please choose the SLR appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding activity 6 “Contact the SLR authors”. How much do you agree with this activity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR) Process

Activity 6: Update (if necessary) and execute the SLR update protocol

After concluding that an SLR needs to be updated, the next activity is to perform the full SLR update. In this activity, the protocol information gathered should be revisited to elaborate the new SLR protocol update [1, 9, 34, 35]. The goal of visiting the protocol is to verify if the new

SLR update will address different protocol steps from the original SLR. However, it is worth mentioning that some protocol information is already defined, such as the search strategy using forward snowballing due to its proven suitability and efficiency [8].

With the protocol revised and ready, the next step is to execute it. To perform the protocol execution, we suggest following the SLR execution activities described in Kitchenham & Charters' guidelines [36] including the application of the selection criteria on the full text of candidate studies, data extraction and synthesis, and finally, answering the SLR research questions.

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding activity 6 "Update (if necessary) and execute the SLR update protocol". How much do you agree with this activity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Full CSLR guidelines and process with references

(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvpK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Regarding Activity 7 “Report/Publish the SLR update”. How much do you agree with this activity?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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(https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mw1HA2PFy2Ooqe89elvepK8RhVqXjWv5/view?usp=share_link)

Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

Continuous Systematic Literature Review (CSLR) Process

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
How much do you agree with the execution flow of the CSLR process, including activities dependent on automation?	○	○	○	○	○

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Please justify your answer. *

Please write your answer here:

Would you change any activity (order of execution)? If yes, which one(s) and why?

*

Please write your answer here:

Would you add, remove or modify any of the activities presented? If yes, which one(s) and why? *

Please write your answer here:

Would you make your SLR data (e.g., protocol, data extraction form, included/excluded study list) available in an open repository (e.g., Zenodo, Github, or a dedicated platform)? Are you interested in tracking this information? Please, justify. *

Please write your answer here:

What is the relevance of having an established process and guidelines that contribute to keeping SLRs in software engineering updated?

Please write your answer here:

According to your experience conducting SLRs, what are the impacts (positive and negative) of the CSLR process and the guidelines presented?

Please write your answer here:

If there are any additional comments (e.g., concerns, suggestions), please describe them here.

Please write your answer here:

Thank you very much for your participation!

2023.02.12 – 17:05

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.